

IMPROVING DINING SERVICE TO FOSTER CUSTOMER DELIGHT IN RESTAURANTS: AN EXAMINATION OF KEY INFLUENTIAL FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to explore the relationship between service quality dimensions and Customer Delight in Casual Dining Restaurants. A descriptive correlation research design was used, utilizing statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and multiple regression analysis. The study investigated two hundred twenty (220) customers from various identified casual dining restaurants in Valencia City Bukidnon. A survey type of research questionnaire- checklist was administered to gather the data needed. The finding of the study indicates a significant association between customer's assessment of dining service and their customer delight exhibiting a high overall multiple correlation ($R=0.475$). This implies that when the customers' satisfaction with the service quality increases customer delight also increases. Furthermore, empathy is also identified as another predictor of customer delight. Suggesting that restaurants that demonstrated empathy towards their customers and guests are more likely to elicit customer delight having the multiple correlation of ($R=0.059$). Additionally, tangibility was also included as a predictor of customer delight implying that the restaurant's attention to tangible aspects added to the total experience of the customers in the restaurant having the multiple correlation of ($R= 0.032$) which means that when customer exceeded their expectation in the tangible aspect of the restaurant there is an increase also with the customer delight. These results emphasize the importance of focusing on service quality dimensions such as satisfaction, empathy and tangibility to enhance customer delight. The higher the satisfaction of participants regards service quality, the greater their tendency to be delighted.

Keywords: *Casual Dining Restaurant, Customer delight, Dineserve, Satisfaction, Empathy, Tangibility*

INTRODUCTION

The food service sector is one of the fastest-growing industries in the current era, and competition has always been fierce. This industry continues to grow every year and is never left behind to keep on innovating and producing a product to cater to the changing food preferences of the customers. The food service industry is an establishment that prepares food, or meals not on the premises of our home (Cousins, et.al 2014). This industry consists of a restaurant, school, and hospital cafeterias, food stalls, and food parks. Their operations continue to enjoy remarkable development and progress together with considerable advances in quality. In this highly competitive industry, restaurant owners and management must find a better way to make their products and services stand out from others. The researcher believes that restaurateurs must know the diverse preferences of the customers.

According to Kukanja and Planinc (2019), the organization must understand the vital role of service quality. They must cater to the needs and wants of each one who visits the restaurant especially when the organization plans to build a better customer relation. In line with this, establishments should ensure that customer satisfaction will exceed the customer's expectations. With the decade-long study of customer satisfaction, it is suggested that satisfaction is not enough to assess the customer experience.

The latest study conducted by Kristiawan et.al (2020), asserted that customer needs and satisfaction can be considered at the center of every successful business. Customer delight is the maximum level of engagement experienced by the guest. This manifests a higher state of emotional arousal and excitement toward the restaurant's customer satisfaction. This statement is supported by the study of Schneider and Bowen (1999) as cited by Torres and Ronzoni (2020) assert that customer delight is created by meeting customers' higher-order wants, specifically self-esteem, as suggested by Maslow's Hierarchy of needs such as recognition.

The researcher believed that the organization needs to be particularly concerned with how customers' views of the service offering change over time. With aggressive competition between all types of food establishments, customers are the best assets. The researcher finds it imperative to determine the link between dining service in restaurants to customer delight. This postulation is supported by the study of Baluyot and Pampolina (2021), who argued that customer contentment on the service provided by the restaurant is essential however it may not be enough to continuously grow sales and beat the competitors. The managers and restaurant owners need to realize that customer delight is an important factor for repeat purchases of the customer and can generate loyalty and greater loyalty-driven profit.

The researcher sees the necessity for the restaurant's management to increase their understanding that not all satisfied customers can devote their loyalty to the establishment. Therefore, it is essential to have a deep understanding of customer delight through the use of dining service dimensions. The researcher believed that to help aspiring and starters entrepreneurs in the restaurant business, they must know the importance of customer delight. A customer who has exceeded satisfaction with the service and product may return to the establishment and become a loyal customers. Based on the study of Torres and Ronzoni (2020), it was mentioned that future research must examine the relationship between satisfaction surveys to delight. Casual Dining Restaurant has a varied customer base from all walks of life. This type of restaurant is serving lesser-priced food with a good ambiance yet providing a very affordable dining experience, thus focusing, on the quality of food to be served. The researcher believed that in order to improve the service of all newly operated casual dining restaurants in Valencia City, the owner, and management needed to understand the level of customer delight that customers experienced during their visit.

There are many newly operated restaurants in Valencia City Bukidnon over the past few years. The researcher believed that to compete with the existing restaurants, the newly opened ones should strengthen their service through exceeded satisfaction that may lead to delight and will be able to gain loyal customers and compete with the fast-growing industry. Moreover, there were no related studies conducted in the restaurant service in Valencia City, thus, the researcher believes the significance of this study for the development and improvement of customer delight in the dining service dimension.

Furthermore, it is assumed that the findings of this study would not only contribute significantly to the improvement of dining service in the food and beverage industry in the said locality but also would add to the body of knowledge about the dining service dimension, thus, this will study greatly help the newly opened establishment to come up with very strong and different strategies to boost the satisfaction of the customer.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the influence of dining service on customer delight among restaurant guests in Casual Dining Restaurants in Bukidnon. Specifically, the study required to answer the following:

1. How are the participants characterized in terms of age and sex?
2. What is the customers' assessment of the restaurant service in terms of:
 - 2.1 tangibles;
 - 2.2 reliability;
 - 2.3 responsiveness;
 - 2.4 assurance;
 - 2.5 empathy;
 - 2.6 price; and
 - 2.7 Satisfaction.
3. What is the level of customer delight among the guests of restaurants in Valencia City?

4. Does customer delight vary when grouped according to their demographics?
5. Do the participants' quality service assessment significantly influence Customer delight?

METHODOLOGY

This study applied the technique of quantitative method approach specifically the descriptive correlational research design which is appropriate to determine the influence of dining service on customer delight among restaurants in Valencia City Bukidnon.

A random sampling method was used in choosing the participants of the study. The participants of the study were the 220 customers of casual dining restaurants in Valencia City, Bukidnon as recommended by the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator with a 5% margin of error, and a 95% confidence level drawn from the customers of different newly operated casual dining restaurant in the city with a total of 500 people who visited these restaurant aged 15 yrs. old up to 60 yrs. old and above with a 50% response distribution.

The researcher adapted and modified the DINESERV instrument developed by Markovic et al (2010) and divided the survey instrument into two parts. The first part was a 32-item scale that constituted seven dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, price, and satisfaction. The following items comprising the said dimensions are as follows 1-5 are for Tangibility, items 6-10 for Reliability; items 10-13 for Responsiveness; items 14-18 for Assurance, items 19-23 for Empathy; items 24-28 for Price, items 29-33 for Satisfaction. The second part is the adapted survey questionnaire developed by Torres et al., (2017) to measure customer delight.

Certain protocols were observed in gathering the data. First, the researcher addressed a letter to the City Mayor's Office of Valencia City, Bukidnon, requesting permission and statistics on how many new establishments were launched in 2022 and early 2023. When the permission and data were provided the researcher established contact with the owner and asked permission to conduct the survey and at the same time explain the benefits of joining the study. The owners of the restaurant voluntarily participated in the study and the questionnaire was subsequently distributed to the customers of the said casual dining restaurants. The researcher assured the restaurant owners of the confidentiality of the data.

Impacts were assessed using a five-point Likert scale with values of "Strongly Agree," "Agree," "Slightly Agree," "Disagree," and "Strongly Disagree." To organize the data, the following statistical tools were utilized: Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were employed to determine the assessment of the participants as regards the dimensions of dining service and customer delight. The correlation analysis was used to determine the association between dining service and customer delight. To find out the significant relationship between various dimensions of

dining service and customer delight, ANOVA was utilized. To determine the customer delight of customer, regression was used.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the participants in terms of gender. The table reveals that the majority (60%) of the participants are females compared to their male counterparts which is only (40%). This implies that most of the customers patronizing the service in casual dining restaurants are females.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Participants (Sex)

Gender	F	%
Male	87	40
Female	133	60
Total	220	100.00

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the participants in terms of age. This table presents the majority (65%) of the participants belonging to young adulthood with ages ranging from 20 – 39 years.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Participants' Age

Range	Age Level	F	%
60 yrs. old and above	Older Adult	7	4
40-59 yrs. old	Middle-aged Adult	26	12
20-39 yrs. old	Young Adult	144	65
15-19 yrs. old	Teenager	42	19
Total		220	100.00

Customers' assessment of the restaurant service in terms of:

- 2.1 Tangibility,
- 2.2 Reliability,
- 2.3 Responsiveness,
- 2.4 Assurance,
- 2.5 Empathy
- 2.6 Price; and
- 2.7 Satisfaction

Table 3 presents the customer assessment of the casual dining restaurant's service in terms of tangibility.

Table 3. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Casual Dining Restaurants Service (Tangibility)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	70	32.00
3.40 – 4.19	High	112	51.00
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	24	11.00
1.80 – 2.59	Low	14	6.00
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		220	100
Overall Mean		3.80	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.72	

No.	<i>The restaurant has...</i>	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1.	Visually attractive parking area and building exterior.	3.18	Moderate	1.25
2.	Visually attractive dining area.	3.90	High	0.83
3.	Staff members who are clean, neat, and appropriately dressed.	4.06	High	0.63
4.	Décor in keeping with its image and price range.	3.99	High	0.84
5.	Thoroughly clean restrooms.	3.90	High	1.08

Table 4 shows the customers' assessment of the casual dining restaurants in terms of reliability.

Table 4. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Casual Dining Restaurants Service (Reliability)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	104	47.00
3.40 – 4.19	High	83	38.00
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	26	12.00
1.80 – 2.59	Low	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	7	3.00
Total		220	100
Overall Mean		3.99	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.77	

No.	<i>The restaurant...</i>	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1.	Served food and beverages in the promised time.	4.15	High	0.88
2.	Quickly corrects anything that is wrong service.	3.87	High	0.96
3.	Is dependable and consistent.	3.87	High	0.91
4.	Provide an accurate guest check.	3.96	High	1.01
5.	Served food and beverages exactly as ordered.	4.16	High	0.82

Table 5 presents an assessment of the casual dining restaurant service in the responsiveness dimension.

Table 5. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Casual Dining Restaurants Service (Responsiveness)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	40	19.00
3.40 – 4.19	High	112	51.00
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	53	24.00
1.80 – 2.59	Low	15	6.00
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		220	100
Overall Mean			3.80
Interpretation			High
SD			0.81

No.	<i>Responsiveness. The restaurant staff...</i>	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1.	Maintains speed and quality of service during busy times.	3.93	High	0.84
2.	Provides prompt service and quick.	3.76	High	0.83
3.	Give extra effort to handle special requests.	3.75	High	0.91

Table 6 shows the customer assessment of the casual dining restaurants' dimensions in terms of assurance.

Table 6. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Casual Dining Restaurants Service (Assurance)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	47	21.00
3.40 – 4.19	High	121	55.00
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	44	20.00
1.80 – 2.59	Low	8	4.00
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	0	0.00

		Total	220	100
		Overall Mean		3.94
		Interpretation		High
		SD		0.75
No.	<i>The restaurant staff...</i>	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1.	Can answer questions completely.	3.95	High	0.91
2.	Makes customers feel comfortable and confident in dealings with them.	3.84	High	0.82
3.	Are willing to give information about menu items, their ingredients, and method of preparation.	4.00	High	0.94
4.	Makes customers feel personally safe.	4.05	High	0.86
5.	Are well-trained, competent, and experienced.	3.71	High	0.77

Table 7 presents the customer assessment in casual dining service in terms of empathy dimension.

Table 7. Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Casual Dining Restaurants Service (Empathy)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%	
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	22	10.00	
3.40 – 4.19	High	138	63.00	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	43	19.00	
1.80 – 2.59	Low	17	8.00	
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	0	0.00	
Total		220	100	
Overall Mean			3.75	
Interpretation			High	
SD			0.74	
No.	<i>Empathy. The restaurant...</i>	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1.	Has employees who are sensitive to the needs and wants of customers.	3.77	High	0.73
2.	Makes customers feel special.	3.80	High	0.69
3.	Anticipates customers' needs and wants.	3.62	High	0.93
4.	Has employees who are sympathetic and reassuring if something goes wrong.	3.75	High	0.79
5.	Keeps customers' best interests at heart.	3.77	High	0.90

Table 8 shows the customer assessment of the casual dining restaurant service in terms of price dimension.

Table 8. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Casual Dining Restaurants Service (Price)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	60	27.00
3.40 – 4.19	High	107	49.00
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	45	20.00
1.80 – 2.59	Low	7	3.00
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	1	1.00
Total		220	100
Overall Mean			3.99
Interpretation			High
SD			0.81

No.	Price	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1.	The menu items offered are reasonably priced.	4.06	High	0.88
2.	The menu price is fair enough given the portion size.	3.91	High	0.88
3.	The food has a good value for the money given.	3.86	High	0.92
4.	The price of the food is appropriate to the services provided.	3.93	High	0.93
5.	The menu price is fair for the quality of the dishes.	3.93	High	1.07

Table 9 presents the customer assessment of casual dining service in terms of satisfaction dimension.

Table 9. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Casual Dining Restaurants Service (Satisfaction)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	42	19.00
3.40 – 4.19	High	113	51.00
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	50	23.00
1.80 – 2.59	Low	14	6.00
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	1	1.00
Total		220	100
Overall Mean			3.73
Interpretation			High
SD			0.89

No.	Satisfaction	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1.	Customers' overall satisfaction with the dining experience.	3.82	High	0.83
2.	Customers will likely return to the restaurant.	3.70	High	0.92
3.	Customers will recommend the restaurant to others.	3.80	High	0.89

4.	The restaurant provides excellent quality service.	3.72	High	1.02
5.	Customers are satisfied with the quality of food and beverages.	3.66	High	0.98

Level of customer delight among the restaurants in Valencia City

Table 10 presents the customer assessment for customer delight.

Table 10. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Assessment of Customer Delight

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	%
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	13	6.00
3.40 – 4.19	High	124	57.00
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	58	26.00
1.80 – 2.59	Low	25	11.00
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		220	100
Overall Mean			3.53
Interpretation			High
SD			0.86

<i>Customer Delight</i>	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1. I felt special	3.68	High	1.02
2. I felt welcome	3.81	High	0.81
3. I felt like a unique customer	3.37	Moderate	1.06
4. I felt acknowledge	3.65	High	0.96
5. I had a pleasurable experience	3.48	High	1.09
6. I felt empowered as a customer	3.35	Moderate	1.07
7. The staff was flexible	3.64	High	0.92
8. The service was worth my time	3.57	High	0.88
9. I received a positive surprise	2.98	Moderate	1.18
10. The staff was friendly	3.85	High	0.96

4. Does customer delight vary when they are grouped according to their demographics?

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the customers' delight when customers are grouped according to their demographics.

Table 11 presents the personal demographics of the participants in terms of sex in relation to Customer delight.

Table 11. Result of the test of Difference on Participants' Assessment of Customer Delight in Terms of Sex

	Male		Female		t	P
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Customer Delight	3.54	0.80	3.58	0.75	1.243	0.217

Table 12 presents the test of difference of the participants' assessment of customer delight according to their age.

Table 12. Result of the test of Difference on Participants' Assessment of Customer Delight in Terms of Age

Cases	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Age	1.926	5	0.385	0.644	0.667
Residual	128.052	214	0.598		
Total	129.997	219			

5. Do the participants' assessment of quality service significantly influence Customers' delight?

Ho2. The customers' assessment of the restaurants' dining service does not influence Customers' Delight.

Table 13 presents the result of the regression analysis of Customer Delight.

Table 13. Regression Analysis of Dining Service as Predictor of Customer Delight

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.091	0.146		7.485	0.000
SAT	0.665	0.038	0.764	17.475**	0.000
2 (Constant)	0.357	0.156		2.291	0.023
SAT	0.412	0.045	0.474	9.103**	0.000
EMPA	0.447	0.054	0.428	8.217**	0.000
3 (Constant)	0.163	0.166		0.984	0.326
SAT	0.363	0.047	0.417	7.678**	0.000
EMPA	0.363	0.060	0.348	6.059**	0.000
TAN	0.181	0.060	0.169	3.032*	0.003

Model Summary

R = .834

Adjusted R² = .691

F = 164.929**

p = .000

**Significant at the .01 level (two-tailed)

DISCUSSION

The demographic profile of the respondents as observed by the researcher during data gathering showed that the number of female participants who visited the establishments was greater than males. Atulkar and Kesari (2018), stated that gender can control the buying characteristics of a consumer resulting in impulse buying which highly supported the result showing that most of the customers patronizing the service for casual dining restaurants are females. In addition, Ahn, (2020), espoused that, males and females choose to purchase or buy products however majority of members in the loyalty program were females.

In terms of age, the finding reveals that most of these young adults patronize casual dining restaurants. Surucu et. al, (2020), posited that young adults prefer to purchase the product and services they trust to avoid risk associated with purchasing unknow products. This is followed by those who belonged to the teenage group with ages ranging from 13-19 years old. However, it is interesting to mention that among the group, the older adults had less frequency of visiting casual dining restaurant service. This is not surprising since this type of customer with ages ranging 60 years old and above are generally conscious of their diet; hence, they most likely prefer to dine in fine dining restaurants or at home where their diet requirements can be satisfied. Ahn (2020) stated that age and income were significantly related to the buying preferences of the customers. The data show that the majority of the participants are young professionals who have the capacity to visit and dine in casual dining restaurants.

In regards with the participants assessment of dining service dimension specifically tangibility. The table shows that the customers are generally satisfied with the restaurants as indicated in the overall mean of 3.80 interpreted as high. This means that customers are satisfied with the restaurant's physical factors of the restaurant such as the dining area, décor, rest room including the physical appearance of the staff. The researcher observed that participants pay attention to how the restaurants look as a whole. It is also noticed that the décor of the restaurants adheres to the restaurants' theme; even the staff were professionally dressed and groomed. In the result presented in Table 3, it can be gleaned that the staff members who are clean, neat, and appropriately dressed received the highest assessment rate with a mean of 4.06 interpreted as "high". This implies that customers are not only considering the interior and appearance of the restaurant but also the physical aspect of the staff. In the same vein, visually attractive parking areas and building exteriors received the lowest rate with a mean of 3.18 interpreted as moderate. This means that the customer's expectation for the parking lot is below the level of their criterion since the majority of the restaurants do not provide a wide parking space to accommodate customers. These findings confirm the study presented by Suciptawati et.al (2019), which posited tangible dimensions related to services such as building

interior and exterior, furniture, the appearance of the restaurants, and well-dressed employees as a factor for the satisfaction of the customer.

In reference to the preceding table, the researcher believed that since the majority of the customers are from the working class, they were exposed to tangible things through their experience with restaurants. The result is also in accordance with the study of Pakurar et.al (2019) which postulated that the restaurants' interiors, exteriors, appearance, and uniform of the staff are tangible aspects of the restaurant used in order to provide the needed service.

Moreover, in Table 4, the findings reveal that the customers rated the restaurant staff with an overall mean of 4.00 interpreted as high. This means that the staff's way of providing and serving the order surpassed customer expectations. This result is in accordance with the study of Ramya, et. Al (2019) states that reliability is the capacity to provide the promised service consistently and precisely. Serving food and beverages exactly as ordered received the highest mean score of 4.16 interpreted as "high". This means that the staff was able to meet the expectation of the customer to receive their order exactly as they ordered. This result conforms with the study of Zygiaris et.al (2022) stated that accountability and quality are factors that contribute to reliability. The researcher observed that the service provided and delivery of food to the customers were exactly delivered as ordered. It is also noticed that the staff were able to serve and deliver the food ahead of the given time.

In the same vein, they rated the restaurant as dependable and consistent which got the lowest rate with a mean of $M=3.87$ also interpreted as "high". This means that the customers were satisfied with the services offered by the casual dining restaurants should be consistent.

Furthermore, table 5 shows that the customers rated the staff high as indicated in the overall mean of 3.81. This means that customers were satisfied with the way the wait staff provided the services. When the restaurant is very busy, the staff was able to maintain the quality of service given to the customer as observed by the researcher, hence this area had the highest assessment from the customer as indicated with the overall mean of 3.93 interpreted as "High". The foregoing finding is supported by the study of Wijoyo et.al (2022) which stated that responsiveness is the willingness to provide immediate and appropriate quality service. In the same vein, giving extra effort to handle special requests received the lowest assessment with a mean of 3.75 but still interpreted as "high". This means that the customers were satisfied with the effort of the staff to handle special requests therefore the expectation of the customer for a good service meet.

As for the dimension of assurance, it is presented in the table that the customers rated the staff with an overall mean of 3.94 interpreted as "high" which means that the customers are satisfied with how the staff assured them of their safety in dining in their restaurants. The researcher observed that the staff is willing to answer every inquiry of the customer even without assurance that the customer will dine in their establishment. The staff can give exact information on what the customer needs to know about the menu.

This act is supported by Anwar and Abdulla (2021) who pointed out that assurance is the ability of the staff to be courteous, build rapport, render trust, and confidence, and be knowledgeable. It is imperative for the restaurant staff to prove that visiting their establishment and availing of the products and services is trustworthy and worth the money they are paying.

In this current study, making customers feel personally safe got the highest mean of (4.05) interpreted as “high”. This means that the staff was able to let the customers feel that they were safe in their establishment by means of giving correct information about the menu and the ingredients of the food and that the customers were generally satisfied with the way the wait staff handled the queries from the customer. This finding is supported by Ali et.al (2021) who posited that assurance is the ability of the staff to inspire the customer with confidence and trust. Furthermore, no matter what type of customer visits the restaurant, the staff should create a trustable environment. Customer trust and confidence in the establishment, service, and products may lead to an increase in the profitability of the restaurant.

Dimension of empathy was rated high by the customer as shown in the overall mean of 3.75. This means that the customer was satisfied with the service provided and the way the staff appreciated each customer. The researcher observed that the restaurant was able to hire staff who were sensitive to the needs and wants of the customer. This gesture is supported by the study of Umasuthan et al., (2017) which asserts that empathy is a moral emotion. This dimension, making customers feel special stood out having the highest mean of 3.80 interpreted as “high”. This means that the customers feel that they are well-valued and that their presence is important in the establishment. In the same vein, anticipating customers’ needs and wants had the lowest mean of (3.62) yet is still interpreted as “high” which means that the customers’ expectations in terms of staff’s anticipation of their needs and wants were met by the staff.

For the price dimension, the data reveal that the customers rated the price an overall mean of 3.99 interpreted as “high”. This means that the customers were satisfied with the price of the food. The quality of food and service compensates with the amount of money they are paying. The researcher observed that the menu price was affordable which is commensurate to the quantity of food being served. The findings were supported by the study of Feinberg, B., and Wooton, I., (2020) stating that price determines whether customers will patronize the product and services again. In this dimension, the menu items offered are reasonably priced and got the highest mean of (M=4.06) described as high. This indicates that the clients were pleased with the quantity of food on the menu. In the same vein, the food that has a good value for the money given received the lowest rate with a mean of 3.86 described as “high”. This finding is supported by the study of Dyatmika & Firdaus, (2021) espoused that price plays a vital role in customer preferences.

Lastly on dining service dimension is satisfaction. The customer rated this dimension with an overall mean of 3.73 described as “high”. This means that the customers were satisfied with the overall service of the restaurant and the staff. The researcher also saw the quality of service provided by the staff which contributed to the

customers' satisfaction. In this dimension, customers' overall satisfaction with the dining experience received the highest rate with a mean of 3.82 described as "high" this indicates that the consumer is satisfied with their dining experience and is willing to suggest the establishment to others. This finding is supported by Aburayya et al., (2020) who defined satisfaction as the reason that customers may lead to long-term retention and recommending the service to others. Moreover, the customers are also satisfied with the quality of food and beverages which received the lowest assessment as indicated by the mean of 3.66 interpreted as "high". This means that even customers are generally satisfied with the quality of food and beverages, but this is an area that needs to be examined further by the restaurant management.

In regard to the assessment of customer delight, the customers rated this area as high as indicated in the overall mean of 3.53. This means that the customers are delighted with the overall services that the establishment offers. The researcher observed that the staff is very accommodating; the customer feels that they are welcome, valued, and special to the establishment. These findings are supported by Parasuraman (2020), who postulated that customer delight is the emotional imprint left on the customers' attributes; it is the positive and memorable feelings that happen to the customers. The result further shows that the staff was friendly and received the highest rate with a mean of 3.85 or interpreted as high. This means that the effort of the staff to have a positive effect and try to build a rapport by being friendly to the guest in the most truthful way is very effective. This notion is supported by Barnes, et al (2016) who posited that employee effort, affect, and skill are producing factors of delight.

As for the participants' assessment of customer delight in terms of sex, it shows that customer delight has no significant difference ($t= 1.243$, $p= 0.217$) considering their sex, therefore the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This means that whether they are males or females the customers' delight is almost similar, which further implies that their sex is not a source of variation of their customer delight. The result is supported by the study of Torres et.al, (2014), who stated that the service experience of men and women that led them to feel delighted is almost the same.

The assessment of customer delight in terms of age shows that customer delight does not significantly differ considering their age ($F= .644$, $p= 0.667$). Therefore, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This means that the age of the participants is not a source of variation in their assessment of customer delight. This conclusion is corroborated by the researcher's observations made during data collection. The majority of the customers were in the same bracket of age. The perception and expectation of young adults were almost the same in terms of service quality in a restaurant.

Examining the specific dimensions of dining service, satisfaction stands as the highest predictor of customer delight, ($B=.665$, $t= 17.475$). Table results that the model is significant at the .01 level ($F= 164.929$, $p= .000$) with a high multiple correlation ($R=.834$), thus, the null hypothesis can be rejected. Furthermore, 69.1 percent of the variability in customer delight is accounted for by a combination of the dimensions of dining service. ($F= 17.475$, $p=.000$) indicating that for every unit of increase in their satisfaction, there is a corresponding .665 increase in their customer delight. It is, thus,

inferred that satisfaction precedes customer delight implying that customer satisfaction has to be met first before customer delight occurs. The finding is in consonance with the study of Afthanorhan et al., (2019) which posited that satisfaction is achieved when the expectation of the customer is met. As a result, of this satisfaction, the customer would feel delighted.

Further, empathy (Beta .363) is another predictor of customer delight which means that for every unit with an increase in their empathy, there is a corresponding .363 increase in their customer delight ($B=.363$, $t=6.059$, $p=000$). This further means that the higher the demonstration of staff's empathy the more customers are delighted. This notion is supported by the study of Setiono & Hidayat (2022) asserts that knowing the customer by name, including their preferences, needs, and wants is an example of how to empathize with the customer, thus delighting the customers.

Moreover, tangibility places the last predictor of customer delight (Beta .181) indicating that for every unit increase of tangibility, there is a corresponding .181 increase in the customer delight ($B= .181$, $t=3.032$, $p=0.003$). This means that the more comfortable the servicescape the more guests and customers will be delighted. This conception is supported by the study of Kukanja et.al (2019) posited that tangibility is vital for guest satisfaction in the restaurant therefore the higher the satisfaction rate the more customers and guests feel delighted.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it was therefore concluded that there was a significant relationship between dining service and customer delight. The quality of dining service dimensions especially satisfaction, empathy and tangibility serve as antecedents of customer delight. These three dimensions play a vital role as predictors of delight in a restaurant. Satisfaction is the foundation of customer delight having the highest $B=.665$ which only means that customers felt satisfied with the service they received and were more likely to have a positive perception of the restaurant's services and offerings. This satisfaction comes from various aspects such as the quality of food, excellent quality service, accuracy of orders, and the overall ambiance of the restaurant. By consistently exceeding customer expectations the restaurant can build a strong foundation of customer delight. Furthermore, empathy also plays a significant role in enhancing customer delight having a $B=.363$ which only means that the restaurant provides empathetic service such as being sensitive to the needs and wants of the customer, making them feel special, and keeping the customer's best interest at heart. Empathy helps to adopt a positive and memorable dining experience which likely increases customer delight. Lastly, tangibility also plays an important role in achieving overall customer delight having $B=.181$, which only means that the overall aesthetic of the restaurant such as the building interior and exterior, dining area, product price range, and uniform the staff contributed to the exceeding satisfaction of the customer which contributed to customer delight.

Moreover, the result of the study reinforces the researcher's arguments that dining service satisfaction is indeed linked to customer delight. Customers who are able to

exceed satisfaction have greater tendencies to be delighted with the services of the establishment and can build a loyal customer base, generate word-of-mouth, and ultimately thrive in a highly competitive industry.

Recommendations

It is recommended that this study consider expanding and identifying other components of customer delight in the hospitality industry in order to gain more insights into the said components, explore other instruments that would best capture the customers' assessment of the dimension, and increase the number of sample size of the participants and the participating casual dining restaurants to strengthen the generalization of the findings of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To observe the confidentiality nature of the survey and to adhere to the Data Privacy Act, the participants of this study were informed and assured of the confidentiality of the data gathered which will be used only for research purposes and will not disclose any particular details of the participants. After the tabulation of data, all questionnaires

were kept safe by the researcher and subject for shredding or burying on the ground after 5 years.

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